

A Coatrack for one's Mind: Proposing a new Theoretical Model for the Study of Children's Rights in Context

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Abstract

Several children's rights researchers have expressed concern about a lack of foundational theory/ies in children's rights research. In reply to this discussion, this article proposes the Children's Rights Normative Cultures (CRNC) model, a theoretical model that can guide the study of children's rights realisation in various societies. The model focuses on the normative societal structures surrounding children, representing and integrating the complex set of factors that enable children's rights realisation in specific contexts. In addition to presenting the model, the article outlines existing explicit and implicit theoretical models currently used in children's rights research, and illustrates the model's application in Flanders (Belgium) and Ethiopia.

1. Introduction

Over the past decades, there has been a debate among children's rights researchers on whether or not the field of children's rights research is missing foundational theory/ies (Rynaert et al. 2025; Hanson and Peleg 2020; Quennerstedt 2013). Hanson & Peleg describe children's rights as "a field that is notorious for its absence of (one coherent and sufficiently convincing) theory" (2020: 16), but challenge this proposal. They argue that

children's rights theories, which are not necessarily explicitly posed but can be both implicit and explicit, are not scarce but rather abundant. They come under different forms and for different purposes. Theories can be normative or explanatory, sophisticated or straightforward. They can be borrowed from elsewhere or developed from within the children's rights framework.

As examples, they provide the following list:

the implementation gap theory; top-down versus bottom-up approaches to children's rights; the child, parents and state triangulation; vulnerability and victimhood theories; participation rights as voice, space, audience and influence (or as ladder); children's evolving capacities; recognition theory and the capability approach; autonomy and participation; agency and citizenship; the violence against children framework; the four general principles; and the best interests of the child (2020: 16).

As children's rights researchers who together have substantive experience studying children's rights in a large variety of contexts, we do feel like something is missing. While we greatly value the theories mentioned by Hanson & Peleg (2020), what we are missing is a theoretical model that represents and integrates the complex set of factors that enable children's rights realisation (i.e. violation and/or protection) in a specific context. Such a model, which would enable researchers to study this complexity, is needed, because children's rights realisation cannot be understood in a vacuum. For example, to understand why girls in Sudan are often subjected to female genital cutting, it is not sufficient to study state and international law (Tønnessen et al. 2017); to understand systematic exclusion of Roma children in European societies, it is not sufficient to study EU policy (Sardelić 2017); to understand child marriage in Bali, it is not sufficient to study international norms and practice (Horii 2020). The context in which children live, which shapes the (potential for the) realisation of their rights, is considerably more complex – and the field of children's rights research is in need of conceptual tools and models to adequately capture this complexity.

This paper aims to address this gap by proposing a theoretical model that we believe could be useful for the study of children's rights realisation in various societies. Specifically, we will focus on the normative societal structures that enable or hinder this realisation, which taken together we call a society's "Children's Rights Normative Culture" (CRNC, see section 3). As an explanatory framework, the model not only allows researchers to map various factors relevant for children's rights realisation; it also enables the analysis of the interaction between these factors, identified as normative orders, socio-legal positions, and behaviours and attitudes, within a society. In doing so, it offers a conceptual structure for understanding how normative structures shape the meaning and practices of children's rights in context. Children's rights are here understood in a broad sense, not limited to the articles of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) (Freeman 2020, 8; Rynaert et al. 2025). Instead, they are understood as those norms referred to as "children's rights", which are codified or determined by any normative order of a society, of which international law is one. In general, we assume that CRNCs differ across societies, that they can be studied, and that such knowledge would be useful to both children's rights researchers and practitioners.

In this paper, we present the first outline of such a theoretical model. To present a fully developed theoretical model would require substantive empirical testing, and as such goes beyond the scope of this paper. Instead, we provide a starting point for what we believe such a model could look like.

The paper is divided into two parts. The first part argues for the need of a theoretical model as mentioned above, by discussing the meaning of relevant concepts such as *theory* and *theoretical model* (§ 2.1), and by pointing at a gap in existing literature through an analysis of theoretical models used in scholarly work on children's rights (§2.2). The second part presents

the proposed novel addition to the field of children's rights research: its philosophical foundation (§ 3.1), a theoretical model for the study of Children's Rights Normative Cultures ("CRNCs", § 3.2), and a brief discussion of its potential applications (§ 3.3). To further clarify the theoretical model, the last section of the paper presents two illustrations of the CRNCs of, respectively, Flanders (Belgium) (§ 4.1), and Ethiopia (§ 4.2).

The collaboration for this paper was shaped as follows: [author 1] initially developed a first version of the CRNC model, based on literature study and her past experience with empirical data collection in various contexts. She then reached out via social media to ask whether other scholars would be interested to discuss the idea, and was subsequently invited by various scholars, resulting in visits to Ghent University (Sara Lembrechts, Ellen Desmet and Giselle Corradi), and Jimma University ([authors 2, 3, 4]). In both places scholars (and, in Belgium, practitioners) engaged in critical debate of the model, leading to its further development. In Jimma, colleagues actively joined in further developing this research paper, including authoring the case illustration of the CRNC in Ethiopia.

2. Existing theoretical models in children's rights research

2.1 What is a Theoretical Model?

Bingham et al. describe theory as 'one of the most widely misunderstood concepts in research' (2024, 14). According to Abend, 'confusions about the meaning of 'theory' [in sociology] have brought about undesirable consequences, including conceptual muddles and [...] miscommunication' (2008, 173). We agree, and would argue that clear understanding and consensus of the meaning of "theoretical model", "theoretical framework" and "conceptual framework" are equally lacking, especially seeing that these concepts are often used interchangeably (Bingham et al. 2024; Varpio et al. 2020; van der Waldt 2020; Kivunja 2018; Achinstein 1965).

For the purpose of this paper, based on Achinstein (1965), a "theoretical model" refers to 'a set of assumptions about a system that describes an inner structure of that system'. Formulating a theoretical model is useful where it makes sense to represent a system as having a certain structure, and the actual structure of the system is 'something like [the model], though quite possibly more complex (or in many cases known to be more complex)' (ibid., 104).

The assumptions that are part of the theoretical model can be understood as theories. A theory is defined here as a statement on how concepts relate to each other based on research findings (found through either inductive or deductive methods), which is not obviously true, meaning that it could be refuted by other research (e.g. if based on empirical data: '14-17 year old children in the Netherlands would like to vote, if given the choice'). By contrast, a fact is a statement that is very obviously, without reasonable doubt, true (e.g. 'Children in the Netherlands are not allowed to vote in national elections').

2.2 Theoretical Models in Children's Rights Research

Based on the list of children's rights foundational theories provided by Hanson & Peleg (2020, cited above) we can identify three types of theoretical models: participation rights models (Lundy 2007; Hart 2008), child development and evolving capacity models (e.g. Piaget 1952; Bronfenbrenner 1979; Kohlberg 1984), and capabilities approach models (Sen 1999; Nussbaum 2000). Each of these three types of models offers a set of assumptions about a

(sub)system related to children's rights. More specifically, the structure of the system represented by these models is the system of universal children's human rights / child development. They offer ideal types for childhood and children's rights realisation, against which reality is compared. Consequently, for each of the models, questions have been raised regarding their cross-cultural applicability (Salva 2024; Hart 2008; Henze-Pedersen and Bengtsson 2024; Robeyns 2006; Charusheela 2008; Burman 1994).

When analysing recently published children's rights scholarship (at least the part published in English), we do find implicit theoretical models underlying many of these studies, as predicted by Hanson & Peleg (2020), which do map (part of the) normative structures surrounding children. The first and most prominent theoretical model is the "rule of (formal) law model". This model is based on the Westphalian state system, and it assumes that what children's rights are, or should be, is dictated by the law. "The law" is generally taken to refer to international, regional and/or domestic (state) law, and limited to the formal, written type of law. Whenever there is a violation of children's rights, this means that either the three levels of formal laws are not well aligned, whereby international law and in particular the CRC is understood as the "most correct"; or, it means that the law is not well enforced (e.g. Musembi 2024; Barnes Macfarlane 2024; Coscini 2024; Griffiths et al. 2024).

In reply to this, a smaller group of scholars posits a "legal pluralist" model, of which the basic idea is that to understand law, we need a broader definition of what constitutes as law in a society. It may include laws issued by non-state authorities (e.g. religious law), as well as laws that are unwritten (e.g. ethnic group law) (Corradi and Desmet 2015). To understand children's rights issues, all these types of laws need to be included in analysis (Hopman 2021; Horii 2019). A third approach has been to look at children's rights from a "norm pluralist" perspective. In existing literature on social norms, such norms are often understood to exclude legal norms (e.g. Bicchieri 2017; Hechter and Opp 2001; Elster 2007). In general, it is usually implied that a children's rights researcher needs to choose between either local, social norms (bottom-up approach) or (inter)national laws (top-down approach) (Corradi and Desmet 2015; Hanson and Nieuwenhuys 2013; Liebel 2012), a situation probably caused by the disciplinary backgrounds of its proponents: roughly, legal scholars use top-down approaches, while anthropologists use bottom-up approaches.

A core theoretical problem with these approaches is how to distinguish between legal and non-legal societal norms, and whether such a distinction really benefits the academic understanding of children's rights. Also, how to choose between bottom-up or top-down approaches (and why would we have to choose anyway?). The problem is navigated by some scholars by stating that they are using "socio-legal methods" (e.g. Gawu and Koblavie 2024; Haddad 2024). This concept seems sufficiently wide and undefined, referring to something like "studying legal norms in a societal context", leaving room for many factors to be considered. However, its definition and applications vary widely, and concrete theoretical models and methodologies are lacking (Creutzfeldt et al. 2020; Tamanaha 1997). An alternative and more comprehensive, yet less often used, approach is when all societal norms together are analysed systematically from a broader norm pluralism perspective, which includes both legal and non-legal societal norms (e.g. Hopman and Smajić 2023). However, we may find a 100 different norms in a society, but simply listing these norms still doesn't tell us how they relate to each other, how they relate to people's behaviour and attitudes, nor how they work to realise children's rights.

Therefore, a model that integrates the complex set of factors that enable children's rights realisation in a specific context needs to be more comprehensive than both currently existing explicit and implicit theoretical models in children's rights research.

3. A New Theoretical Model to Study Children's Rights in Context

Below, we present a starting point for a theoretical model to study children's rights in diverse societies. We begin by briefly discussing the philosophical foundation of the model (§ 3.1), before detailing its core components (§ 3.2), and discussing its potential scientific use (§ 3.3). The next section will illustrate the application of the model by suggesting what two societies (Belgium (Flanders, § 4.1) and Ethiopia (§ 4.2)) might look like when studied through the lens of the CRNC model.

3.1 Philosophical Foundation

We start with a (brief) philosophical foundation, found in Rothenberg's theory of the excessive subject as a carrier of the possibility for societal change (2010). Rothenberg shows that all people, as subjects, are constantly creating meaning. As a result, in the relation between subjects who create and re-create (signify) meaning, we create society. On the one hand, we try to solidify meaning so that our society becomes stable. On the other hand, we are constantly changing meanings and thereby changing society, because as subjects, we are always in excess: we are always seeking something, yet never finding it. This is a necessary condition for both the subject and society (if we did not have this excess, we would literally do nothing, and there would be no society, and no subject).

To understand children's rights in context, we suggest to capture those relatively stabilised meanings in society that contribute to the realisation of children's rights, referred to as "children's rights normative cultures" (CRNCs). Indeed, these are *relatively* stabilised meanings, since the social space is always in the process of being both dissolved and regenerated (Rothenberg 2010, 204; see also Kaime (2010) and Corradi (2017)). In addition, we should pay attention to the affects, defences and fantasies of subjects in relation to the normative culture and, more specifically in our case, children's rights, since here lies the possibility for social change (Rothenberg 2010, chapter 7).

3.2 Children's Rights Normative Cultures (CRNCs)

In all societies we find complex normative structures which guide the choices of individuals. These structures vary among societies, and as structures, enable or prevent the realisation of children's rights, while simultaneously (re)defining the content and meaning of such rights. This model uses the term "normative culture" to describe the collection of existing normative structures in a society. A normative culture consists of three core elements: a) socio-legal norms, created by various social orders ; b) the patterns of behaviour and attitudes that society members have towards these norms; c) the socio-legal position of society members. Norms are defined as 'rules that state how people ought to behave' (Kelsen 1911). Normative culture, as defined here, can be schematised in the following manner:

Figure 1. A schematic presentation of the normative culture theoretic model.

“Socio-legal norms” refers to all norms that regulate human behaviour which are social in nature. This includes both legal norms, from legal normative orders (e.g. international law, state law, religious law) as well as non-legal social norms, from non-legal normative orders (e.g. family norms, community norms).

“People’s behaviour and attitudes” refers to how people behave in relation to these normative orders and their norms (e.g. conform or resist), as well as their attitudes towards the normative orders and its norms (e.g. respect or disrespect). Under this heading we find all kinds of individual motivations in relation to socio-legal norms, both normative motivations (e.g. ‘I know the law says that we should do A, but I think we should do B’) and non-normative motivations (e.g. ‘I think we should do A, but I want to do B’). It also includes situations when individuals are not aware of certain socio-legal norms, and/or when they hold false beliefs about such norms – which may influence their behaviour and attitudes. Overall, people’s attitudes relate to both the normative order as a whole as well as to specific norms, whereas behaviour, with the exception of protest, is mainly concerned with specific norms. Here we find the ‘affects, defences and fantasies of subjects’ which Rothenberg (2010) argues hold the key to social change.

Lastly, “Socio-legal position of society members” refers to the socio-legal position people hold in society (e.g. child/adult, national/non-national, girl/boy, Muslim/Christian). Different socio-legal norms apply usually to different socio-legal groups, both formally and in practice; people who identify as members of certain socio-legal groups will therefore experience certain norms as binding on them; and enforcement of norms can also vary greatly depending on the socio-

legal group concerned. This is where we find reasons for in- and exclusion of groups, including all forms of discrimination.

All three core elements of normative cultures are interrelated. For example, state law might create certain socio-legal positions (e.g. child/adult) and determine which legal state norms apply to people in either category; people may also self-identify as belonging to a certain group (e.g. Muslim/Christian) and therefore certain religious norms do or do not apply to them. Socio-legal norms are shaped and heavily influenced by people's attitudes (e.g. to some extent people can co-create their own normative family order), and socio-legal norms (can) influence people's behaviour (e.g. through enforcement). If someone agrees with a certain norm (e.g. 'Christian girls should not attend school'), they are more likely to enforce this norm towards the specific socio-legal group to whom the norm applies. If they disagree with the norm, they are more likely to try to change the norm through various forms of protest.

In short, the model represents the dynamic interaction in societies between norms, attitudes, behaviours, and socio-legal positions. The core elements are equal in weight, and one can look at a children's rights situation from either of the three angles. For example, one could start with a child's socio-legal position, e.g. taking Roma children living in Belgium as the starting point for investigation. One could also start from behavioural aspects, e.g. studies on school attendance. Lastly, one could start from certain normative orders, e.g. starting with mapping the social norms prevalent in a certain neighbourhood, or the legal norms in a certain state.

For the model to lead to an explanation of how the CRNC enables children's rights realisation in a specific society, it is crucial to go beyond a mere list of factors, and to study exactly this interaction between the three core elements. To this purpose, we suggest three guiding questions:

1. What is the relation between the three core elements, particularly: where lies the centre of normative power (in other words: overall, which normative order has most power over the child's life)?¹
2. What is the meaning of children's rights within the CRNC according to the various normative orders; according to individual members; and in relation to various socio-legal positions of children?
3. How are normative decisions, in particular decisions (not) to prioritise children's rights, aligned with practical decisions (e.g. if education is considered of high importance, to what extent are resources allocated to this topic?)

3.3 Potential Applications

We see four main potential applications of the model.

First, to guide the study of a specific children's rights situation for a particular (subgroup of) society. When designing a study on for example "the child's right to education in the UK", or "the right to healthcare for immigrant children in Japan", the model provides an overview of factors to study. In this case the CRNC of a society is mapped only in relation to that specific

¹ The concept is derived from Pospisil's notion of the "center of legal power" ((Pospisil 1967, 17)).

children's rights situation being studied - while, of course, keeping in mind that children's rights are interconnected and interrelated (Goonesekere 2020).

Second, to generate general insight into the normative societal context (i.e. CRNC), which can be used as background knowledge for children's rights researchers and practitioners working in that society. Knowledge of a societies' CRNC can be used as a starting point for designing a specific study, or as a foundation to designing interventions. Such insight can range from a quick CRNC scan, to an in-depth study of the CRNC of a certain society.

Third, once we know the CRNC of a society, we can use this knowledge for comparative analysis – either between children's rights ideals and the normative structure of society, or between various CRNCs. Example research questions include: “Which elements of the CRNC of [society A] explain the high level of occurrence of [children's rights violation X] in this society?”, or: “Which parts of the CRNC in [society A] can be mobilized to prevent or mediate [children's rights violation X]?”, or: “Which elements of the CRNC in [society A] create an environment wherein [the child's right to X] is realised, and what might [society B] be able learn from this situation, seeing their similarities/differences in CRNC?”

Fourth, the model provides conceptual tools for thinking about children's rights realisation at a more abstract or theoretical level (e.g. “What might be the meaning of the child's right to participation across various cultures?”).

Regardless of which approach is chosen, we expect that the resulting knowledge can support children's rights actors in designing effective children's rights interventions, and by academics to deepen the understanding of children's rights in context. As one expert in Flanders summarized it, during an early discussion of the model: it provides “a coatrack for one's mind” (*“een kapstok voor uw hoofd”*).

4. Illustration: two cases

Below, we present analyses of the CRNCs of two societies: Flanders (Belgium), and Ethiopia. These analyses are not comprehensive, but must be read as illustrations to the theoretical model, to further clarify its meaning and use. They are based on limited data, resorting from literature study and consultations with a limited number of adult experts. For a comprehensive analyses of these particular CRNCs, we find that multiple empirical methodologies should be applied, first and foremost involving children and adults from various socio-legal groups.

4.1 The CRNC of Flanders (Belgium)

4.1.1 State and International Normative Orders and their Interrelations

Since 1993, Belgium is a federal state. The federal state consists of three regions (Flanders, Brussels and Wallonia), three communities (Flemish, French and German), 11 provinces, and 589 municipalities (Devroe et al. 2017, 62). All these entities are normative orders. The regions and the communities, as well as the federal state, have their own governments and parliament (Debaenst 2023, 112-113), which are democratically elected. Their territories overlap (see figure 3):

Figure 2. Regions and communities in federal Belgium (Deschouwer 2004, 22).

Competencies are divided at the federal level between the three types of normative orders, with most competencies being situated at the regional level.²

There is no formal hierarchy between federal, regional and communal laws (Debaenst 2023, 127, 133). European and international laws are for the most part directly applicable in Belgium, and in hierarchy, formally, stand above national laws (Debaenst 2023, 126, 138-139). At the same time, there seems to be increasing legal power vested at the local municipality level (Devroe et al. 2017). The authors summarise the relation between Belgian state normative orders as follows:

To draw upon a classic distinction between steering and rowing made in the study of governance (Osborne and Gaebler 1993), regional authorities steer social policy responses (policy formulation, e.g. agenda setting, allocation of resources) to quality of life issues; federal authorities steer law enforcement and maintenance of public order; municipal authorities are obliged to row (i.e. implement) both criminal justice and social policy approaches (2017, 62).

However, the competencies of the municipality seem to go beyond mere execution of law created elsewhere, resulting in similar actions leading to different consequences between municipalities. For example, young people displaying antisocial behaviour in municipality Antwerp are offered ‘a variety of programmes and services’, and in case of non-compliance, issued a fine. In municipality Liège, they receive a warning, and in case of non-compliance, the case is referred to the state legal justice system (Devroe et al. 2017). A children’s rights expert working for a Flanders municipality mentioned that they ‘legislate’. When asked, she said that she meant ‘create policy’.

² For an overview, see: https://www.belgium.be/en/about_belgium/government/regions/competence, accessed 24 June 2025.

According to Debaenst, this fragmentation of legal orders results in ‘a rather complicated state structure, including the fragmentation of competences and institutional responsibilities [...] There are, for instance, ministers of four different governments competent for matters regarding the environment or energy in Belgium, causing all kinds of problems.’ (2023, 113).

4.1.2 Socio-Legal Positions of Society Members and their Normative Orders in relation to State Normative Orders

Formally, all children are treated equally by state and international law in Flanders. At the same time, there are many other socio-legal normative orders which create norms for children. These groups are directly related to the socio-legal position of society members, and their norms to some extent have more influence over children’s lives than the state level norms. Below, because of limited space, we discuss two.

First, the nuclear family (“*gezin*”), consisting of the parents and children, seems to have a central place in norm creation and application over children. For example, the region provides all kinds of services to parents and children (e.g. free vaccination programs, subsidised childcare, free education, “upbringing support”), but leaves it up to parents to decide whether or not to make use of such services (Detraux et al. 2010; Theeten et al. 2013; Ghysels and Van Lancker 2010; Meerschaert et al. 2004). Professionals are instructed to ‘respect the socio-cultural habits and beliefs of the parents’ (Detraux et al. 2010, 89). Relevant socio-legal positions connected to the nuclear family as referred to in studies are for example the socio-economic group to which the child – as part of the nuclear family - belongs (e.g. working class, middle class or high class (Vanhoutte and Hooghe 2013)), or the type of household that the child lives in: single-parent or parent-couples (married or unmarried) (Verhetsel and Witlox 2006; Statbel 2025a). Children’s rights realisation is expected to be influenced by membership of such groups.

Second, ethnic groups. Around 28% of the population of Flanders has a foreign background (Statbel 2025b). One well-documented example of an ethnic group normative order in Flanders are Turkish Belgians. A study among this ethnic group by Van Kerckem et al. (2014), shows that Turkish Belgians (200.000 in total, according to Taras (2012, 260)) constitute a strong normative order. The authors describe how among Turkish Belgians group norms serve to preserve the group as group, by drawing symbolic boundary markers between Turkish Belgians and native Belgians. One of the most important norms is the norm of female chastity: ‘A “Turkish” woman is not supposed to engage in premarital sex, should not be seen in the company of men not related to her, and should spend most of her time at home, especially in the evening’ (Van Kerckem et al. 2014, 284-285). Generally, group members are pressured ‘not to assimilate too much but to conform to those norms, values, and cultural practices that are deemed central to the ethnic group’s identity’ (ibid., 279). These group norms are enforced through ‘informal sanctioning mechanisms such as gossip, loss of honor, social exclusion or ridicule’. The most extreme measure that is used to sanction non-conformity is excommunication from the community or repudiation by the family (ibid., 279).

4.1.3 People’s Behaviour and Attitudes

In the hierarchy of normative orders and their norms, “the law” generally holds a central position in Flanders – there is a general attitude of respect for, and sense of authority of, the (formal state) law. For example, a specialist on inclusive education in schools remarked that when they have a discussion with a school regarding the inclusion of a certain child with special

needs, ‘we then present our legal framework, [to indicate] that [they] do not have a choice’ (*‘Wij komen met ons wettelijk kader: je [schooldirectie] moet.’*), implying that a legal reference is the end to the discussion, since everyone understands that what is in the law must be done.

Many studies on norms in Flanders or Belgium focus on legal normative orders (e.g. Devroe et al. 2017; Vandenbroeck 2006; Verhetsel and Witlox 2006; Detraux et al. 2010; van de Pol and Vanheule 2018; Debaenst 2023). At the same time, most people don’t know the content of the (many!) laws, and the law is considered a highly specialized area of expertise (Debaenst 2023, 127, 131).

From the perspective of people of Flanders, the main normative order, where we find the center of normative power, seems to be the regional normative order (i.e. the Flanders region). For example, academic colleagues from Flanders indicated that they did not exactly know, nor were particularly interested in, the complexities of the Belgian legal system, and recommended focusing on the region instead; similarly, children’s rights expertise centres operate at the regional level. The regions divide different language communities: Dutch-speaking (Flanders), French speaking (Wallonia), and a minority German speaking group (Wallonia/German community), which also contributes to people feeling addressed mainly by the norms of their own region, addressing them in their own language. According to Billiet et al.,

Apart from Brussels and the surrounding area, Flemish and francophone politics form two different worlds. The media report only to a limited extent on the politics of the other region [...] Primarily as a result of this media gap, two different cultures have gradually emerged, with diverging social sensitivities, fashions and customs (2006, 913-914).

However, for a member of the Turkish-Belgian ethnic group, the normative order of this socio-legal group might very well be dominant. In general, from the child’s perspective, it is not unlikely that the nuclear family as normative order would be experienced as dominant over the regional order, since much space is given by the legislator for families to decide over their children (see § 4.1.2).

4.1.4. Children’s rights: meaning and practical decisions

The meaning and content of children’s rights in Flanders seems to be derived mainly from the international law (CRC) and the regional level (Jeugddecreet 2023). Political decisions at the regional and municipal level are aligned with these legal instruments, and budget is allocated accordingly: the budget for youth policy in Flanders was 65.6 million Euros for 2023, which is 0.1% of the total Flanders budget; the budget for education and training was 18.082 billion Euros (European Commission 2024). Priorities are determined, and subsequently funded, at the regional level (Ministerraad Vlaamse Regering 2025). Financially, the regional and federal state are responsible for the realisation of children’s rights for all children living in Flanders.

4.1.5 Conclusion and further research

In a few words, the CRNC in Flanders is one of fragmentation, overlapping responsibilities, and the contradiction of a strong idea of positivist state/regional law as the centre of normative power, combined with local autonomy. In practice, this means for example that various children’s rights organisations may be working on the same or similar topics in the same area with limited coordination, and that local level normative orders (e.g. the nuclear family or an

ethnic group) have far-reaching autonomy to decide over children, while being offered optional services by many public institutions.

The information presented above is necessarily limited in scope, particularly because it leans heavily on literature study, and literature on children's rights norms in Flanders has largely focused on state and international legal norms. More research on these local normative orders and their role in children's rights realisation, as well as into people's behaviors and attitudes towards the various normative orders, and various socio-legal positions of society members, is necessary to further understand the CRNC of Flanders and to map potential for societal impact.

4.2. The CRNC of Ethiopia

4.2.1 Socio-Legal Structure of Ethiopia

Ethiopia is a legally pluralistic state, as it is home to diverse ethnic groups where federal and state laws coexist alongside various customary and religious normative orders (Tezera 2020). Formally, Ethiopia was restructured as a federal state in 1995, encompassing nine national regional states and two city administrations. The regions are organised along ethnolinguistic lines although diverse ethnic groups reside across regions (Fessha and Beken 2013; Van der Beken and Sisay 2025). Powers are shared between the federal and regional governments. The federal government is vested with powers and functions of formulating and implementing national policies and strategies, establishing and administering national security forces, formulating and implementing foreign policy, negotiating and ratifying international agreements, formulating the country's financial and monetary regulations, including the budget allocation (Habib 2010; Sherif 2021). The regional states are autonomous in making their own legal norms through their respective legislative bodies, consistent with federal laws (Halefom 2022 FDRE constitution, art. 52(1)). They are also authorized to govern their internal matters and can collaborate with federal and neighbouring regions when necessary. All regions have their own distinct boundary demarcations (see figure 4).

Figure 4. Regions in ethnolinguistic Ethiopia federation. Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Regions_of_Ethiopia.

Legally, children are recognised as rights bearers through the ratified international United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child and the regional instrument of the African

Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (ACRWC). Additionally, children's rights are integrated in many federal laws, such as the Revised Family Code (2000), the Criminal Code (2005), and the National Child Policy, to mention a few (Alemu and Birmeta 2012). According to the state laws, a child is defined as any person under 18 years of age (Mulugeta and Baynesagn 2025).

While the legal state norms essentially appear as the dominant normative order on paper, they are less applied at the grassroots (community and family) level. In society members' everyday lives, ethnic and religious norms are generally more popular and more applicable in shaping community structures relevant to the realisation of children's rights (Assefa 2012). Some of these customary norms, including indigenous conflict resolution mechanisms, are also recognised by the federal laws, hence further strengthening their legitimacy in society. For example, since 2021, the Oromia region has recognized and established customary courts to operate parallel to state courts at the *kebele* (lowest administrative unit) and district levels by Proclamation No. 240/2021. The customary court uses Gadaa laws (Oromo customary laws), and its judges are elders. The Amhara, Sidama and Southwest Ethiopia regions have adopted similar legislative measures by their respective councils. Other regional states are likely to follow similar patterns adhering to the directions given by the Federal Ministry of Justice (van den Bergh and Metekia 2024).

4.2.2 Socio-Legal Positions of Society Members

In most Ethiopian societies, the socio-legal positions of children are primarily shaped by three sets of non-legal normative orders: the collective nature of society, the entanglement of rights and duties, and authoritarian-patriarchal norms/social hierarchies.

Despite variations in naming and practice across ethnic and cultural groups, communal living is a common customary norm among Ethiopian societies, where individuals are required to participate in community networks in order to be considered meaningful members of society (Abebe 2008, 2025). Collective life is organised so that people depend on the extended family, friends, and neighbours for their existence. They also form different associations, such as *iddir* (burial associations), *iqqub* (rotated savings club), and *debo* (festive labour exchange groupings). These are some of the collective life systems through which individuals offer one another financial, social and emotional support in everyday lives and in times of hardships (Kebede and Butterfield 2009; Poluha 2004). Ethiopian children's everyday lives and rights are also intertwined with this communal way of living. Children are positioned as integral members of the family and community. They are not regarded as independent right holders, but rather their rights are entwined with communal duties. Children are raised collectively, as they belong to the clan, not only to their biological parents.

The second set of customary norms relevant to children's rights realisation is the inseparability of children's rights from responsibilities. Children have responsibilities to the family and society at large. Parents and community members are also responsible for meeting the physiological and psychological needs of children. Children's contribution to the family and community wellbeing is expected in accordance with their capacity and ability (Abebe 2008, 2013; Abebe and Tefera 2014; Ayele 2021). This customary norm positions children as contributors to the wellbeing of family and community, not only as being helped, acknowledging their agency.

A third set of relevant customary norms relates to the authoritarian-patriarchal nature of social hierarchies in society. The family and society are structured based on seniority, and adults have a vested authority over children, including the power to instruct and control them (Abebe 2007). Moreover, men and women, and boys and girls, do not possess equal powers. At the household level, male heads have more power over women and children, especially in areas of decision-making and resource control. In women-headed families, senior women have power over younger females and boys. Male children expect their sisters to serve them, while older siblings of each gender have some authority over younger ones (Bevan and Pankhurst 2007). Culturally, there is a hierarchical social relationship between children and adults, where children often take the subordinate positions, particularly in the areas of decision making and resource control.

4.2.3 People's Behaviour and Attitudes towards Customary and Legal Normative Orders

Among most Ethiopian societies, ethnic and religious norms hold central power in shaping people's behaviours in their daily lives. Rather than formal normative orders, where the majority of people, particularly in rural areas, have less awareness about the contents of the existing laws, ethnic and religious norms are more prevalent and powerful in guiding individuals' everyday behaviours and attitudes. The majority of society members also show conformity with and respect for the ethnoreligious norms. Many customary norms are created and enforced at the level of the family, community and ethnic group. Children are also taught to be respectful and obedient to ethnoreligious norms. They must respect teachers, parents, and older siblings (Camfield and Tafere 2011; Poluha 2004), as customary norms oblige them to do so. These norms are enforced by parents and other adults in the community, sometimes with the use of physical punishment (Wonde et al. 2014).

To illustrate further how this functions, we have chosen to describe some elements of the CRNC of the Oromo ethnic group. The Oromo, an ethnic group consisting of over 40 million of Ethiopia's population, is the largest ethnic group in the country. They live predominantly in Oromia National Regional State, geographically spanning Ethiopia's central, western, southern, and south eastern plateaus and lowlands (Abebe 2021; Fekadu 2009; Schlee 2018).

The Oromo normative order is based on an indigenous political system called *Gadaa*. This political body, membership of which is exclusive to all male members, is divided into five classes, each holding political power for an eight-year term. Each class comes to power in rotation of every forty years. It establishes, enacts, and amends Gadaa laws during its term, including norms pertinent to the protection and care of children (Wako and Chala 2025).

However, the level of normative power of the Gadaa system varies across Oromia. Gadaa normative system is stronger among the Borana and Guji Oromo compared to other Oromia zones. Furthermore, due to the large population size of the Oromo and the extensive territory they inhabit, they experience various ecologies, adhere to different religions, maintain diverse livelihoods, and interact with multiple cultural groups, all of which directly influence their daily practices (Wako & Chala, 2025). Below, we highlight some examples of children's rights related norms from the Gadaa normative system, which applies to all Oromo, but is particularly powerful among the Borana and Guji Oromo (ibid.).

One example of Gadaa norm relevant to children's rights is *guddiffachaa*. Guddiffachaa is the term for a set of norms that together make up a voluntary system of adoption in which biological parents or other family members give one of their children to be raised by adoptive

parents. Guddiffachaa is set up and applied when the biological parents are unable to provide for the child, the adoptee is an orphan, or the adopting parents are childless. For the orphan child, the extended family members take responsibility of arranging adoption process. The parents, the community, and the elders who organize the adoption enforce its implementation (Dida and Daraje 2023).

Another relevant Gadaa norm among the Oromo is the norm of premarital virginity for girls (one among many gendered norms). This is a socio-culturally deeply rooted norm, which is manifested through several practices, such as female genital cutting (FGC), early marriage, and assigning masculine identity, including masculine identity markers (hairstyle), to unmarried girls (Emirie 2005; Gemechu and Mekuria 2021). For example, the Borana Oromo consider all unmarried girls to have masculine identities. As their identity marker, these girls share hairstyles with boys while they wear ornaments, like necklaces and bracelets, which the married women do not. Having sex with unmarried girls is strictly forbidden and considered a homosexual act. The community and family are responsible for protecting the girl's premarital virginity, and the Gadaa leaders severely punish men who have sex with unmarried girls (Chala and Haro 2023). FGC and early marriage, as practices that prevent pre-marital sex for girls, are forbidden by state law (Revised Family Code, 2000), yet because ethnoreligious norms are dominant and more valued by members of the society, the Oromo and other ethnic groups uphold these norms and related practices through covert actions - without the knowledge of the state actors. They do so for example by misrepresenting the age of the child to state institutions, or by conducting FGC secretly and/or by paying a fine or bribing state law enforcement officials afterwards (Tesfaye et al. 2024). This behaviour demonstrates the general attitude of the Oromo people towards the ethnic group norms, clearly holding them in higher regard and shaping their behaviour in accordance with these norms rather than with state law. It also shows that when the state attempts to enforce its norms upon the people (e.g. by fining those who conduct FGC), because of their attitude towards state versus ethnic group norms, the Oromo find ways to resist state norms and conform to ethnic group norms instead.

Consequently, the ethnic norms, shape how family life, childhood and children's rights are construed and practiced in Ethiopia (Kassa and Abebe 2016).

4.2.4 Conclusion and further research

Overall, Ethiopia's child rights normative culture comprises complex and pluralistic normative orders that overlap - complementing one another on some issues, contradicting on others, and sometimes engaging in struggles over power and authority. For most Ethiopian children, especially those in rural areas, the ethnoreligious norms are more dominant and powerful normative orders that prescribe and shape children's positions and daily lives in society. The ethnic group normative order should therefore be considered the centre of normative power within the CRNC of Ethiopia. Ethnoreligious norms stem from a number of more general customary practices that are shared among all ethnic groups. Other relevant socio-legal normative orders in are is the federal and regional state laws, which are mostly the language of individuals working in the formal system, such as government and nongovernmental organisations (Adejumobi 2007; Epple 2020). As the information presented here is limited in scope and depth, further empirical research is needed to examine how the CRNC facilitates or hinders children's rights realisations across Ethiopian societies.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented a first version of a new theoretical model for the study of children's rights in context, called the "Children's Rights Normative Culture (CRNC) model". We have described the existing gap in literature, presented the model, suggested possible applications, and illustrated its application to two case studies (Flanders and Ethiopia).

As indicated, the aim of the model is to represent the normative structure surrounding children insofar as this structure enables the realisation of their rights, whereby the content of these rights is continuously (re)defined within this same structure. As an explanatory framework, it allows researchers to map various factors relevant for children's rights realisation, and offers a framework for understanding how normative structures shape the meaning and practices of children's rights in context, by analysing the interaction between the three core elements of CRNCs: socio-legal norms, socio-legal positions, and people's behaviours and attitudes.

We expect that the model can be used both by children's rights researchers and practitioners, to four purposes: to guide the study of a specific children's rights situation for a particular (subgroup of) society; to generate general insight into the normative societal context; to support comparative analysis of children's rights realisation; and to provide conceptual tools for thinking about children's rights realisation. As one expert in Flanders summarized it: the model provides "a coatrack for one's mind" (*"een kapstok voor uw hoofd"*).

Although the model is developed based on our collective experience studying children's rights situation in various societies, including empirical work in each of these studies, it has not yet been fully tested in its application, except the preliminary studies of the CRNC of Flanders and Ethiopia shared here. We expect that the model can be refined and further developed based on further theoretical research, expert discussion and empirical testing, and would welcome any such input from colleagues around the world. Our hope and expectation is that the model can be used by children's rights actors to design (more) effective children's rights interventions, and by academics to gain more comprehensive understanding of children's rights in context.

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